

STUDY OF THE POSSIBILITY OF USING BRICK BREAKAGE TO PRODUCE CERAMIC CONCRETE

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Abstract

The paper considers the possibility of solving the problem of disposal of man-made products in the form of ceramic brick breakage, formed as a result of the demolition of buildings and structures, using it as aggregates in concrete. The article presents the analysis and results of the study of demolition waste of buildings and structures to improve the efficiency of using this product as an aggregate in the production of concrete composites.

Keywords: brick fight, red brick, secondary raw materials, waste disposal, concrete composites, properties of ceramic concrete

In the modern world, the construction of buildings and structures is gaining more and more pace every year. The rapid construction process is connected, on the one hand, for the developer to build quickly and reliably, and on the other hand, to offer the consumer high quality housing and its durability.

As a result of the planned demolition of obsolete buildings and structures, as well as natural and man-made disasters, large volumes of scrap from concrete, reinforced concrete and brick breakage are formed, which should first of all be used in construction [1-3].

The main structural material for various types of construction at present and in the foreseeable future remains concrete and reinforced concrete. Therefore, expanding the possibility of using waste for the manufacture of various concretes is an urgent problem. This is especially true for lightweight concrete. Such concretes on porous aggregates are used to reduce the dead weight of load-bearing structures [2].

The use of broken red brick for the manufacture of some building products is of great national economic importance, both in terms of saving resources and in terms of waste disposal to ensure environmental safety. At the same time, the experience of using crushed bricks (the so-called opacum) as an active hydraulic additive to increase the water resistance of lime binders has been known for a long time.

At present, it seems promising to use ceramic production waste to obtain cementless awakened concrete and mortar. Awakened concrete is a plastic hardening building material, which is obtained by partial grinding on heavy brick runners and other waste materials in the presence of water and an activator (most often lime, sometimes cement, etc.). The above examples show that the raw material base of the construction industry can be significantly expanded through the processing and rational use of various waste products from the construction industry.

This article discusses the possibility of developing and justifying a technical solution for the use of ceramic brick breakage in the manufacture of concrete composites, in order to reduce the cost of concrete and environmental pollution.

In this regard, the authors of the work propose to use in construction a relatively new, practically free, secondary building material, which before that, at best,

was used as a backfill for the roadway, and at worst, into a landfill, this is a brick fight.

Thus, based on numerous experiences and studies, aimed at studying the structure and properties of secondary building materials from technogenic raw materials, the authors propose to use red brick cullet as a fine and coarse aggregate in the ceramic concrete technology. In addition, it has been experimentally proven that the secondary aggregate from brick slaughter is an alternative to traditional expanded clay.

To study the possibility of using production waste in the manufacture of building materials and products in the educational and scientific laboratory, experimental studies were carried out. The information given in various literary sources shows that the use of broken brick in lightweight concrete, instead of expanded clay, can reduce its cost by 30-35%. Broken brick, as a secondary material obtained during the demolition of brickwork, has the same structure as the original material - brick has its own design strength and durability, having a porous structure.

As fine and coarse aggregates in the studies, secondary products of crushing brick slaughter were used - brick crushed stone and sand, as well as natural dense quartz sand to control the density and strength. Tests of the compositions and properties of aggregates from the products of crushing brick slaughter were carried out in accordance with GOST 8735-88 "Sand for construction work. Test methods" and GOST 8269.0-97 "Crushed stone and gravel from dense rocks and industrial waste for construction work. Methods of physical and mechanical tests". Research has established that the products of red brick processing have the same structure as the original material - brick, which has its own design strength, durability and porous structure. The most important quality indicator of aggregates is their grain or granulometric composition. To study the broken brick and the product of its processing, its grinding was carried out using a jaw laboratory crusher DS-200ShL. Then, on the basis of a set of sieves (GOST R 51568-99), an analysis of the granulometric (grain) composition of aggregates from brick slaughter was performed.

To assess the suitability of aggregates from ceramic brick cullet, the following was studied:

- content of dust and clay particles;
- ratio between crushed stone and sand fraction;

- the ratio of partial and total remains of crushed stone, on a standard
- a set of sieves;
- modulus of fineness of sand from brick fight

Based on the results of sieving crushed material from brick slaughter on a set of sieves with mesh sizes from 0.16 mm to 40 mm, the following ratio of crushed stone and sand fractions was established (1).

Table 1

The results of sifting crushed brick battle on sieves 5-40

Name of crushed raw material	Content of fraction grains, mm, in the crushed brick product, % by weight			
	0-5	5-10	10-20	20-40
1	2	3	4	5
brick fight	27.6	9.75	24.0	38.6

The number of particles less than 5 mm (sand from screenings of brick crushing) is about 25-30% of the mass of crushed raw materials. The results of sifting sand from the battlefield on a standard set of sieves and are shown in table 2.

Table 2.

The main characteristics of brick sand

Indicator name	Indicator values						
	Sieve size, mm	2.5	1.25	0.63	0.315	0.16	Bottom
Residues on sieves, g	224	120	165	305	81	120	
Private residuals, %	22.4	12.0	15.2	30.7	8.1	12.0	
Complete balances, %	22.4	35.0	49.2	80.0	88.1	100	

Other basic properties of sand from the battle of bricks are as follows: fineness module-2.6; content of dust and clay particles- 0.2% ;clay content in lumps -0 % ;strength of sand under compression in the cylinder-10.8(108)MPa (kgf/cm²);true density of grains- 2580 kg / m³ ;fill void- 1170 kg / m³ ;water absorption-12% by weight ;porosity- 16%;sand voidness-33%

The modulus of fineness of sand from screenings of brick crushing is 2.6, which corresponds to the group - coarse sand according to GOST 8736-93. The sieving

graph (Figure 1), which characterizes the grain composition of sand from the screening of brick crushing, shows that the resulting curve is almost entirely located in the area of admissible values of fine aggregate for lightweight concrete. The section of the curve at the grain interface of 2.5 mm, which goes beyond the recommended range of sand values, has an insignificant value of the grain composition index of sand from brick slaughter. Thus, the obtained secondary sand from brick slaughter can be recommended for the preparation of concrete composites .

Figure 1. - The curve of screening sand from the screening of crushing brick slaughter, plotted on the graph of the grain composition of fine aggregate

This sand from brick slaughter, according to the fineness modulus $MK = 2.6$ and the total residue on the sieve 0.63, equal to 49.3%, belongs to the group of coarse sands, and according to the content of grains with a fineness of less than 0.16 mm, it corresponds to class II sand. Coarse aggregate (crushed stone) from

brickwork, as noted above, was fractionated to obtain three fractions - 5-10 mm, 10-20 mm and 20-40 mm. The results of the study of the properties of the secondary large aggregate from the brick battle are presented in table 3.

Table 3

The main characteristics of crushed stone from a brick fight

Indicator name	Indicator values		
Fraction, mm	5-10	10-20	20-40
Bulk density, kg/m^3	863	848	822
Voidness, %	40	45	48
Strength of sand under compression in the cylinder, MPa (kgf/cm^2)	12.1(121)	12.4(124)	13.2(132)
Content of dust and clay particles, %	Not		
Clay content in lumps, %	Not		
True density of grains, kg / m^3	2580		
Water absorption, % by weight	12		
Freeze resistance, cycle	25		
Porosity, %	16		

To control the density, strength, ceramic concrete based on aggregates from crushed bricks, local quartz sand was used, the main physical and mechanical characteristics of which are presented in Table 4.

Table 4

Main characteristics of sand

Indicator name	Indicator values						
The grain composition of the sand	Sieve size, mm	2.5	1.25	0.63	0.315	0.16	<0.16
	Residues on sieves, %	2	4	14	44	34	2
	Private residuals, %	2	6	20	64	98	
Size modulus	1.9						
Content of dust and clay particles, %	2.4						
True density of grains, kg / m^3	2620						
Bulk density, kg/m^3	1560						
Sand density, %	40.5						

According to the results of the study of aggregates made of brick, one can state their compliance with the standards and the effectiveness of their use in the compositions of ceramic concrete.

Thus, on the basis of the foregoing, it can be stated that the use of secondary aggregate from ceramic brick cullet will, firstly, make it possible to subsequently obtain ceramic concrete suitable for both repair and restoration work and for new construction, and secondly, to reduce the negative impact waste to the environment and, thirdly, free up large areas of land for other needs.

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